

USERS' AWARENESS, PREFERENCES AND ATTITUDES TOWARDS REFERENCE SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the library users' awareness, preferences, and attitudes toward the reference services of the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre. It has three (3) research problems that to show the status of the references services and level level of awareness, preferences, and attitudes towards the reference services with the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre by clients.

This study made use of a descriptive-quantitative research design. The UZ college students were considered the respondents of the study. The survey questionnaire was used to gather data. The findings revealed that the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Center's reference services are in very good shape in terms of basic services.

It was then guided by a null hypothesis tested at .05 level of significance which states that there will be no significant difference on the level of awareness, preferences and attitudes on the reference services of the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre, when grouped according to department or college. The status of reference services in the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre in terms of services performed usually is good. The status of reference services in the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre in terms of services performed sometimes is also very good. The respondents were well aware of the reference services offered by the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre. The respondents much preferred the face to face or personal assistance of the reference librarians and reference services, and lastly, a significant difference did exist on the level of awareness, preferences, and attitudes towards the reference services of the Arturo Eustaquio libraries and Information Centre when the respondents were grouped according to departments and colleges. It was concluded that, the status of reference services in the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre was very good.

Keywords: Client's Reference Attitudes, Non-traditional Reference Services, Reference librarian, Reference Preferences, Reference Services, Traditional Reference Services,

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A. INTRODUCTION

Academic institutions play a crucial role in society by educating future generations to use the acquired knowledge to fulfill their responsibilities in a more effective way. The academic library provides a variety of information sources and offers various services for sustaining instructional, research, and learning activities. Thus, libraries in academic institutions are considered to be very essential, often viewed as a core academic activity, and exceedingly vital to the intellectual life of the university. Library services have a significant effect on educational standards and quality.

A reference librarian is essential to the operation of a library. In addition, libraries must have a great collection, an excellent catalog, lots of subject guides, a rich assortment of e-resources, and good signage. However, with no direct assistance to the users, a library will not function effectively. This simply means that a reference service is important in the library.

According to Bunge and Bopp (2001), they categorized reference service into 3 broad groups: a.) Information services that involve either finding the required information on behalf of the users, or assisting users in finding information; b.) Instruction in the use of library resources and services (broadly defined as information literacy skills); and c.) User guidance, in which users are guided in selecting the most appropriate information sources and services.

With this, academic libraries are trying to meet the needs of the academic and research communities by providing and improving their services and enhancing their resources. A successful strategy to enhance the exploitation of resources is to ensure user satisfaction through an efficient and effective reference service. Every library or information center strives to provide accurate and timely information to the right person at the right time in order to satisfy its users.

Today, the Arturo Eustaquio Library & Information Centre's (AELIC) objective is to assist its clientele, especially the students, in their academic and personal development, through the provision of updated library resources and services in order to effectively participate in the attainment of the institutional vision, mission, and objectives and to be more responsive to information demands. At present, the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre is practicing the traditional type of reference service or face-to-face interaction between librarians and library users. These services are not enough, library users are looking for something that can serve them beyond their expectations. According to Asid (2010), that providing quality library service means understanding client needs, providing the right service to meet these needs, implementing a satisfactory delivery system to ensure the service is

appropriate and timely, balancing the resources, and ensuring a constant commitment to the organizational goals.

For so many years, it has been observed that the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre provides the best reference services to library users, but they are still not satisfied or contented with the services rendered by the librarian. This prompted the researcher to make a study of the library reference services entitled: "Users' Awareness, Preferences, and Attitudes towards Reference Services", covering the academic year 2012-2013. Based on the foregoing issues, the researcher intended to assess and evaluate the present status of reference services in the AELIC. As cited by Asid (2010), according to Escalona (2007), that library is an organization within an organization for mostly in academic institution. Different people have different views of what library is.

To this effect, three (3) research questions were posited: 1). What is the status of the reference services in the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre in terms of basic services, services performed usually, and services performed sometimes? 2). What is the users' level of awareness, preferences, and attitudes towards the reference services in the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre? 3). Is there a significant difference in the level of awareness, preferences, and attitudes toward the reference services of the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre, when grouped according to department or college? And 4). On the basis of the findings, what reference services program can be designed to improve or enhance the reference services of the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre?

As a result, the study will be utilized as the basis for designing a state-of-the-art reference service program as well as to upgrade and improve the library services, more specifically the reference service, in order to meet the needs of the users and cope with the trends and demands of modern times.

B. LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORY

This study was supported by Ranganathan's theory of reference services, which explained that reference services are the essence of librarianship and their importance in the context of today's services. His theory of reference services has been worthwhile. It reveals a much deeper service theory than previously thought. Ranganathan believed that effective reference service should be the end of all librarianship. He established that the reference service was the most important work and served as the hub of all library practices.

Ranganathan (1931) stated the five laws of library science that serve as the foundation for reference services. The first law states. "*Books are for use.*" In order to put the book to its

maximum use, it is best to employ a reference service to help the readers help themselves. The second law states, "*Every reader has his book.*" To assist the reader in completing the document search, reference services are required. According to the third law, "every book has a reader." The book cannot travel to the reader on its own. However, reference service will be required to interpret the collection for the reader's query with the document. The fourth law states, "*Save the time of the readers.*" Reference services come to the aid of the researcher and scientist whose time cannot be wasted. The fifth law states, "*Library is a growing organism.*" The collection, the readers, and the time increase to meet altered situations; the kind of reference services will have to be altered to take advantage of technological advances.

According to Kadir (2012), reference services are the services provided by the reference department in a library that helps the library patron to get access to the information that they needed. Reference department provide library user with direction to the library materials, give advice on library collections and services on various kind of information form variety of sources. Reference department basically helps user to answer the questions that the user have in mind as well as helping the user to locate the information that they need in the library.

In terms of Library Services, there should be clear indicators of frequent, judicious and productive use of the library by the students. The following conditions must be present: (1) The library staff gives assistance in the efficient use of library facilities at hours and on days which fit students' schedules; (2) the library provides photocopying facilities; (3) it has reciprocal arrangements with other libraries on the use of library resources (Asid, 2010).

In the study conducted by Tarranza (2006) on library utilization, he reiterated that the library services should be evaluated in order to provide ways of measuring how the library meets the user's needs and satisfaction for knowledge, ideas, and information.

According to Das (2004), the heart of library services is the reference service. Reference service is one of the library's primary functions, along with acquisition, classification, cataloging, and physical planning. In its traditional sense, the term "reference services," sometimes referred to as "reference and information services," can be defined as personal assistance that is provided by trained personnel to library users seeking information. (Das 2004).

He further stressed that the advancements in information technologies have brought about incredible changes in almost every aspect of information services. Reference services are also not an exception. Many new models, new tools, and new ideas have emerged, been implemented, and been accepted into the reference service. However, in spite of all of these changes, the basic functions of reference services have essentially remained constant, such as

providing information. As libraries in the information age become more complex, reference librarians must provide the best service to users. Most users go to the reference librarian to ask questions, and the role of the reference librarian becomes that of a problem solver and consultant.

According to Katz (1992) as cited by Asid (2010) states that the library service has two (2) primary purposes. To provide access to information in many forms and formats and to provide assistance in locating specific pieces of information sought to the needs of the library users- referencing. These services make library as one of the most important elements required to support the teaching and learning process in the elementary, secondary, and tertiary levels of the Philippine education in terms of adequacy of library resources and facilities.

To sum it up, the above-mentioned theories and studies explained that reference service is not simply someone asking a question and someone else providing an answer. It is about someone with an information problem working with someone with information skills. The better the reference services are, the more satisfied the library users will be.

Conceptual Framework

The study intended to evaluate the reference services of the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre to determine the user's level of awareness, preferences, and attitudes towards reference services. Responses from students respondents were solicited to measure the effectiveness of the reference services provided by Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre.

Figure 1. Conceptual Paradigm of the Study
Showing the Relationship of the Independent and Dependent Variables

The respondents were asked to answer the survey questionnaires to determine the library users' awareness, preferences, and attitudes towards the reference services of the Arturo Eustaquio Library & Information Centre. The system approach was used to illustrate the

flow of the study, and this served as a guide for the researcher in the conduct of the study and will finally produce a program on reference services. The first phase was the *Input*, which included the reference services of the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre. The second phase was the *Process* that included the users' awareness, preferences, and attitudes toward the reference services of the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre. And the last stage was the *Output* or the expected result of formulating the reference service program.

C. METHODOLOGY

This study was structured using a quantitative research design employing a descriptive survey method. It attempted to evaluate the status of the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre reference services. A survey study was conducted to solicit information from the respondents to determine the level of awareness, preferences, and attitudes of the library users towards the reference services being provided by the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre.

Respondents and Locale

The study was conducted in the Universidad de Zamboanga. Specifically. It concentrated on the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Center, which houses two (2) libraries, the Main Library and the City Campus Library. These two libraries catered to the information needs of the college students and faculty. The School of Business Management (SBM), the School of Criminal Justice (SCJ), the Department of Civil Engineering (DCE), the School of Education Arts and Sciences (SEAS), the College of Information Technology and Technical Education (CITTE), and the School of Allied Medicine (SAM) are among the six (6) departments.

Research Instruments and Validation

The study utilized a researcher's made survey-questionnaire checklists which comprised the reference services of the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre. A 5-point Likert scale type of questionnaire was employed for numerical ratings with the corresponding verbal description.

The questionnaire composed of two parts. The first part was designed to gather data about the respondents, such as their name (optional) and the department or college. The second part intended to determine the status of the reference services of the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre, Letter A of the questionnaire was composed of constructs on

the three (3) functions of the reference services: 1). Basic services; 2.) Services performed usually; and 3.) Services performed sometimes. The following scales were used:

Scale	Verbal Description
5	Excellent
4	Very good
3	Good
2	Fair
1	Poor

In letter B of the questionnaire, the scales below were used to determine the user's level of awareness of the existence of the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre Reference Services

Scale	Verbal Description
5	Very much aware
4	Much aware
3	Moderately aware
2	Less aware
1	Not aware at all

For letter C of the questionnaire, a construct was made to determine the library users' preferences for the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre Reference Services, wherein the student respondents rate the following reference services according to their preferences: The following scales were used.

Scale	Verbal Description
5	Very much preferred
4	Much preferred
3	Moderately preferred
2	Less preferred
1	Not preferred at all

And for letter D, it is in the form of a checklist on the user's attitude towards the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre Reference Services, wherein choices are given below

for each statement, and spaces are provided for the respondent's answer. The following were used:

Scale	Verbal Description
5	Very high
4	High
3	Moderately
2	Low
1	Very low

To ensure a high degree of validity and reliability of the questionnaire, the research instrument was referred to the adviser for comments, suggestions, and improvement. Then, it was submitted to a panel of experts who have a specialization in library science and/or doctorate degrees to assess the relevance, suitability, and appropriateness of the items to the research constructs, along with a validation form to be filled out with their comments and suggestions. The panel of experts comments and suggestions were incorporated into the final draft of the research questionnaire.

To identify some flaws in the research instrument's reliability, a pilot test was conducted with non-respondent groups who shared similar characteristics as the study's respondents. Then a final draft was produced.

Data Gathering Procedure and Delimitations

The researcher sought permission from the President and Vice President for Academic Affairs to conduct the study. Upon granting the request, the researcher personally distributed the survey questionnaires to the student respondents. Its focus was on whether the library users were aware of the availability of reference services in the library, their most and least preferred reference services, and their attitudes towards reference services. The accomplished questionnaires were retrieved, compiled, and analyzed.

Furthermore, the study was limited to the evaluation of the reference services of the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre as the basis for designing interventions. Its scope was limited to Unversided de Zamboanga where potential library users were considered in this study. This study considered the college students in their respective departments, namely: the School of Business Management (SBM), the School of Criminal Justice (SCJ), the Department of Civil Engineering (DCE), the School of Education Arts and Sciences (SEAS), the College of Information Technology and Technical Education (CITTE), and the School of Allied

Medicine (SAM), who were enrolled during the 2nd semester of the academic year 2011-2012 at the Universidad de Zamboanga as the respondents.

Treatment of Data

Descriptive statistics were used as a statistical treatment in analyzing the data. The following statistical tools were also employed in the analysis of the data:

Frequency. This is the total number of respondents for each item.

Percentage. This shows the distribution of the responses for each construct and item.

Arithmetic Weighted Mean This measure determines the overall average responses of the groups according to the variables.

Analysis of Variance or One-Way ANOVA This was utilized for problem no. 3 to determine the significant difference.

D. RESULTS, DISCUSSIONS, AND ANALYSIS

The data is presented in an order that corresponds to the problem statements in an attempt to answer them congruently. The first research question that this study sought to answer was, "What is the status of the reference services in the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre in terms of basic services, services performed usually, and services performed sometimes?".

Table 2: Level of Status of the Reference Services in the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre in terms of Basic Services

A. Basic Services	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. The library provides general information (Encyclopedia, Almanacs, Dictionaries etc.	4.05	Very good
2. The library provides specific information	3.99	Very good
3. The library provides assistance in locating of documents	3.63	Very good
4. The library provides assistance in the use of the Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC)	3.54	Very good
5. The library provides assistance in the use of reference books	3.62	Very good
Overall weighted mean	3.76	Very good

Table 2 presents the level of Status of the Reference services in the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre in terms of basic services. The result shows that the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre Basic services were very good (3.76). The library provided general information: Encyclopedias, Almanacs, Dictionaries, bibliographies etc. (4.05) and the library provide specific information Mathematics, English, Filipino books, etc. (3.99) obtained the first two highest weighted mean. The finding revealed that the respondents were satisfactory utilizing and receiving the basic services of the library and therefore, the overall status of the Reference services in the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre basic services is very good.

Although the respondents rated the library provides assistance in the use of OPAC (Online Public Access Catalog) had the lowest weighted mean of 3.54, but still, It had the same verbal description of very good. The finding revealed that the assistance on how to use the OPAC (Online Public Access Catalog) was not fully exercised and to some extent not functional. The assistance on how to use the OPAC (Online Public Access Catalog) must be enhanced and improved through library instruction and personal assistance of the librarian was much needed to educate the library users on how to use the OPAC.

Table 3 level of Status of the Reference Services in the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre in terms of Services Performed “Usually”

B. Services Performed Usually	Weighted Meean	Verbal Description
1. The library provides assistance in reservation of documents	3.66	Very good
2. The library conducts Library Instruction/Library Orientation	3.42	Good
3. The library conductsLibrary Tour	3.09	Good
4. The library conducts Library Exhibits (Library Display of New Collection)	3.45	Good
5. The library provides Indexing and abstracting Services	3.47	Good
Overall weighted mean	3.42	Good

Table 3 presents the level of status of the Reference services in the Arturo Eustaquio libraries & information Centre in terms of services performed usually. As gleaned from Table 3, the data show that the overall weighted mean is 3.42 described as Good. The findings revealed that the library was very good at providing assistance in the reservation of documents (3.66). The data imply that the respondents considered this reference service useful in their research.

The data also show that the least reference services that the library performed “usually” was described as Good. In summary, conducting library tours for users was part of the library services, and it must be integrated into the library instruction program. Exploring the physical aspect of the library will showcase the importance of books libraries, and information services in the educational, recreational, and information needs of the academe.

Table 4 Level of Status of the reference Services in the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre in terms of services Performed “Sometimes”

C. Services Performed Sometimes	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
1. The library maintains special files (Archives)	3.68	Very good
2. The library provides reproduction of documents (Photocopy services)	3.72	Very good
3. The library provides reproduction of documents (printing Services)	3.63	Very good
4. The library conducts Book selection	3.76	Very good
5. The library provides Binding Services	3.13	Good
Overall weighted mean	3.58	Very good

Table 4 presents the level of Status of the Reference services in the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre in terms of Services Performed “Sometimes”. The data shown above reveal the library conducted book selection (3.76) and the library provided reproduction of documents through selection (3.76) and the library provided reproduction of documents through photocopy services (3.72) described as very good and obtained the highest mean ratings among the reference services performed “sometimes”. However, the library provided binding services (3.13) considered as the lowest mean rating which is described as good. The findings disclosed that the library must excellently conduct book selection periodically to augment the library resources and to decide whether the library resources will be useful for their intended purpose. On the hand, the library must also provide binding services, since binding services are part of the services that include binding repair and bound periodicals.

Hence, there was a need to improve on this aspect because the library user’s information needs and expectations were continuously changing in the rapidly changing information scenario. Libraries need to re-orient their collections, services, and facilities to keep pace with these advancements.

The Second research question that this study sought to answer is, “What is the users’ level of awareness, preferences, and attitude toward the Reference Services in the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre?”

Table 5 Level of awareness toward the Reference Services in the Arturo Eutaquio Libraries & Information Centre

TRADITIONAL TYPE OF REFERENCE SERVICES	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
<i>I am aware that the library</i>		
1. provides general information (Encycloedia Almanacs, Dictionaries, etc.)	4.02	Much aware
2. provides specific information (Mathematics, English, Filipino books etc.)	3.93	Much aware
3. provides assistance in location of documents	3.72	Much aware
4. provides assistance in the use of the Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC)	3.55	Much aware
5. provides assistance in the use of reference books, etc.	3.66	Much aware
6. provides assistance in the reservation of documents	3.58	Much aware
7. conducts Library instruction/Library Orientation	3.45	Moderately aware
8. conduct Library Tour	3.23	Moderately aware
9. conduct Library Exhibits(Library Display of New Collection	3.44	Moderately aware
10. provides Indexing and Abstracting Services	3.51	Much aware
11. maintain special files 9archives)	3.63	Much aware
12. provides reproduction of documents (Photocopy Services)	3.58	Much aware
13. provides reproduction of documents (printing Services).	3.69	Much aware
14. conducts Book selection	3.61	Much

		aware
15. provides Binding services	3.15	Moderately aware
Overall weighted mean	3.58	Much aware

Legend:

1.00-1.49	not aware at all
1.50-2.49	less aware
2.50-3.49	moderately aware
3.50-4.49	much aware
4.50-5.00	very much aware

Table 5 indicates the result of the users' awareness of the Reference services in the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre. The library provided general information (Encyclopedias, Almanacs, Dictionaries bibliographies, etc.) obtained the highest computer mean of 4.02 with a verbal description of "much aware". While the library-provided binding services garnered the lowest computed mean of 3.15 with a verbal description of "moderately aware".

Based on the analysis of data collected in this study, the results show the library users were much aware of the existence of the reference services offered by the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre, However, there was still a need to improve the marketing strategies of the library in order to promote the library services, specifically the reference services.

This result was supported by Ramos and Abrigo (2011) findings that library users were aware of the traditional type of reference services than non-traditional reference services. Librarians need to proactively promote this kind of reference service to ensure that users may know about the existence of traditional and non-traditional reference services in order to maximize their full potential. According to Radford & Kem (2006), marketing has been highlighted as one of the important factors in library users' awareness. One way of marketing the reference service was to provide prominently and easily access links on the library website.

A total of 168 or 44.44% of the respondents learned the existence of reference services from the librarian; 93 or 24.60 % of respondents learned about reference services from their instructor; 77 respondents learned about it from their friends; 59 of them have read it from the library bulletin; 24 respondents learned about it through library orientation; 21 respondents

learned it from the library brochure. Only 1 out of 378 respondents learned about reference services from others.

Table 6 level of Preferences toward the reference Services in the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre

1. When I went to know basic information about the library, I prefer to ask the libraries through	Weighted Meean	Ranking	Verbal Description
1. Face-to-face (Persoan Assistance)	3.96	1	Much preferred
2. Instant Messaging (Ask-a-Librarian)	3.42	2	Moderately preferred
3. e-mail.reference service	3.20	5	Moderately preferred
4. Facebook (Library fan page)	3.14	6	Moderately preferred
5. Web forms (Library website)	3.22	4	Moderately preferred
6. Voice-over-IP (VoIP) or Telephone conversation though Internet	2.99	9	Moderately preferred
7. SMS reference (Text messaging)	3.04	8	Moderately preferred
8. Searchable Frequently Asked Questions	3.31	3	Moderately preferred
9. Online tutorials	3.07	7	Moderately preferred
10. Video Conference (Skype)	2.89	10	Moderately preferred
2. When I need to request for document delivery, I prefer to do it via			
1. Face-to-face (Persoan Assistance)	3.88	1	Much preferred
2. Instant Messaging (Ask-a-Librarian)	3.33	2	Moderately preferred
3. e-mail.reference service	3.20	4	Moderately preferred
4. Facebook (Library fan page)	3.19	5	Moderately preferred

5.Web forms (Library website)	3.16	6	Moderately preferred
6.Voice-over-IP (VoIP) or Telephone conversation though Internet	3.07	9	Moderately preferred
7.SMS reference (Text messaging)	3.13	8	Moderately preferred
8.Searchable Frequently Asked Questions	3.25	3	Moderately preferred
9. Online tutorials	3.11	7	Moderately preferred
10. Video Conference (Skype)	2.97	10	Moderately preferred
<i>3.When I need assistance in using the online subscriptions, E Journal, etc., I prefer to ask the librarian via</i>			
1. Face-to-face (Persoan Assistance)	3.96	2	Much preferred
2.Instant Messaging (Ask-a-Librarian)	3.36	2.5	Moderately preferred
3. e-mail.reference service	3.22	4	Moderately preferred
4.Facebook (Library fan page)	3.19	5	Moderately preferred
5.Web forms (Library website)	3.18	6	Moderately preferred
6.Voice-over-IP (VoIP) or Telephone conversation though Internet	3.06	9	Moderately preferred
7.SMS reference (Text messaging)	3.10	8	Moderately preferred
8.Searchable Frequently Asked Questions	3.35	2.5	Moderately preferred
9. Online tutorials	3.16	7	Moderately preferred
10. Video Conference (Skype)	2.97	10	Moderately preferred
<i>4.When I need help in looking for specific and highly specialized in the library, I prefer to get assistance from the librarian through</i>			
1. Face-to-face (Persoan Assistance)	4.03	1	Much

			preferred
2.Instant Messaging (Ask-a-Librarian)	3.40	2	Moderately preferred
3. e-mail.reference service	3.23	3	Moderately preferred
4.Facebook (Library fan page)	3.18	6	Moderately preferred
5.Web forms (Library website)	3.17	5	Moderately preferred
6.Voice-over-IP (VoIP) or Telephone conversation though Internet	3.03	9	Moderately preferred
7.SMS reference (Text messaging)	3.13	7	Moderately preferred
8.Searchable Frequently Asked Questions	3.22	4	Moderately preferred
9. Online tutorials	3.10	8	Moderately preferred
10. Video Conference (Skype)	2.97	10	Moderately preferred
5. When I want to request for library orientation, I prefer to do it via			
1. Face-to-face (Persoan Assistance)	3.92	1	Much preferred
2.Instant Messaging (Ask-a-Librarian)	3.38	2	Moderately preferred
3. e-mail.reference service	3.22	4	Moderately preferred
4.Facebook (Library fan page)	3.17	6	Moderately preferred
5.Web forms (Library website)	3.16	7	Moderately preferred
6.Voice-over-IP (VoIP) or Telephone conversation though Internet	3.06	9	Moderately preferred
7.SMS reference (Text messaging)	3.19	5	Moderately preferred
8.Searchable Frequently Asked Questions	3.24	3	Moderately preferred
9. Online tutorials	3.12	8	Moderately

			preferred
10. Video Conference (Skype)	2.99	10	Moderately preferred

Legend:

1.00-1.49	not preferred at all
1.50-2.49	less preferred
2.50-3.49	moderately preferred
3.50-4.49	much preferred
4.50-5.00	very much preferred

Table 6 shows the results of the users who preferred the Reference Services in the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre. When the respondents wanted to know basic information about the library, they preferred to ask the librarian through Face-to-Face or Personal Assistance, which yielded the highest weighted mean of 3.96. it was followed by Instant Messaging or Ask-a-Librarian and Searchable Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) that yielded a weighted mean of 3.42 and 3.31, respectively. Video Conference (Skype) yielded the lowest weighted mean of 2.89 which was considered the least preferred non-traditional reference service. The data imply that the users still preferred the Face to Face or Personal assistance of the reference librarian. According to Ramos & Abrigo, (2011), library users wanted an immediate answer to queries pertaining to library rules and regulations, services offered, and schedules.

When respondents liked to request document delivery, they preferred to do it Face-to-Face, which yielded a weighted mean of 3.88 and all the other indicators are moderately preferred. The least preferred reference service tool in document delivery was Video Conference (Skype) through the internet (2.97). This simply shows that library users preferred quick responses to their needs.

Respondents were also asked what reference service they most preferred to use when they need help in looking for specific and highly specialized resources in the library, and also when they want to request library orientation, the respondents preferred the same, Face-to-face or personal assistance, and the least preferred was the Video Conference (Skype). It simply shows that our library users were more practical nowadays because they were using the more sophisticated tools in asking queries about the library, research and some basic information were quite expensive. Their reason was, they have to use the available resources in the library because they were paying the library fees.

The respondents favored traditional over non-traditional reference services, when they wanted to learn more about the library when respondents liked to request document delivery when they needed assistance in using the library resources when they needed help in looking for specific and highly specialized resources in the library, and when they wanted to request for library orientation, they preferred to receive those mentioned above reference services through Face-to-Face with the reference librarian. Studies have proven that Face-to-Face or personal assistance of the reference librarian continues to be the most used reference service and at the same time, it is the first choice for getting help in the library (Ramos & Abrigo, 2011). Nevertheless, other web-form reference services can satisfy the needs of library users who work outside the library. Therefore the presence of a reference librarian was still much needed even if we have the internet or other online services. Librarians are too important to be a dwindling voice in our society.

Table 7 level of Attitude toward the reference Services in the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre

ATTITUDE TOWARDS REFERENCE SERVICES	Weighted Meean	Verbal Description
1. The librarian helpful	3.92	High
2. The librarian are approachable	3.81	High
3. I feel confident visiting in the library	3.99	High
4.I feel comfortable asking for assistance in the library	3.81	High
5. I feel confident that I can use the library to meet my information needs	3.92	High
6. I know how to locate most of the materials I need in the library	3.77	High
7.I wish more instructions were available on how to do library research	4.05	High
8.The use of reference services has made reference librarians more efficient	3.77	High
9.The use of reference services toa sk questions and see assistance from the librarian has made my research more interesting	3.78	High
10.Using the library is a great experience	4.02	High
Overall weighted mean	3.88	High

Legend:

1.00-1.49	very low
1.50-2.49	low
2.50-3.49	Moderate
3.50-4.49	High
4.50-5.00	very high

Table 7 shows the Users' attitude toward the Reference Services in the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre. As shown in the above data that the overall weighted mean is 3.88 which is described as "high". All the indicators abovementioned fall on the same verbal description of high." "I wish more instructions were available on how to do library research" (4.05) obtained the highest weighted mean. Followed by Using the library is a great experience (4.02) and "I feel confident visiting in the library" (3.99), "I feel confident that I can use the library to meet my information needs" and "The librarians are helpful" obtained the same weighted mean of 3.92. On the other hand, "I know how to locate most of the materials I need in the library" and "The use of reference services has made reference librarians move efficiently" obtained the same and the lowest weighted mean (3.77) but still described as "high".

The study revealed that respondents had a positive attitude toward the library. Librarians and library reference services. This simply means that library users used to come and go in the library. They were interested comfortable and confident enough to do their research, and assignments, study, and make use of the available library resources in the library.

The third research question that this study sought to answer is, "is there a significant difference in the level of awareness, preferences, and attitude toward the reference services when grouped according to department or college".

Table 8 significance on the level of awareness, preferences, and attitude toward the reference services Differences when the respondents were grouped according to their College/Department

Variables	OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN						F-value	P<.05	Decision on HO
	SAM	DCE	CITTE	SBM	SEAS	SCJ			
Awareness of Library Reference Services	3.41	4.04	3.71	3.44	4.36	3.59	6.478	000**	Reject
Preferences of Library Reference Services	2.93	3.49	3.35	3.22	4.10	3.60	6.614	000**	Reject
Attitude towards Reference Services	3.70	4.65	3.91	3.90	4.49	3.81	6.869	000**	Reject

*Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 8 presents the result of the analysis of Variance (One-Way ANOVA) in the level of awareness, preferences, and attitude toward the reference services when the respondents were grouped according to the college where they are currently enrolled. The findings divulged that a significant difference does exist in the level of awareness preferences and attitude toward the reference services in terms of awareness of Library Reference Services ($t=6.478, p.000$) Preference of Library Reference Services ($t=6.614, p,.000$) attitude of Library Reference Services ($t=6.869, p,000$) with the probability of occurrence under the null hypothesis greater than $\alpha=0.05$ level of significance, therefore the posited hypothesis was rejected since there was a statistically significant difference among the variables tested in the study. As disclosed in the findings, the data imply that the students of the School of Education, Arts and Science (SEAS) were much aware of the library service. In addition, these students vary in their preferences when it comes to library services. However, in terms of attitude towards the library service. The Department of Civil Engineering (DCE) rated the services of the library very high. They perceived that the librarians had judiciously worked on their responsibility to render good services to the users.

The fourth research question that this study sought to answer is, "On the basis of the findings, what reference services program can be designed to improve or enhance the Reference services of the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Centre?"

To respond to this problem a Reference Services Program is designed to improve the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre services.

E. CONCLUSIONS

In light of the findings, this study made the following conclusions:

1. The status of the Reference service of the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries and Information Center in terms of basic services and services perform sometimes is very good. This simply means that the library provides assistance and accurate information effectively.
2. Library users are not very much aware of the reference services being offered or catered by the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre. It simply shows that the library should exert more effort to promote and make the library more viable and significant in the academic community.
3. Library users' were much-preferred face-to-face or personal assistance from the reference services of the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre. This implies that respondents were more satisfied if the reference librarian assisted them personally with their research work.

4. The attitude of the library users towards the reference services of the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre is high. This connotes that respondents were highly at ease with the reference services being rendered by the librarians.

5. Significant difference does exist in the level of awareness, preferences, and attitudes toward the reference services of the Arturo Eustaquio Libraries & Information Centre when the respondents are grouped according to department and college. This simply shows that library users had different needs, the library and librarians should be flexible enough on the changing needs of the library users to effectively perform their roles and meet the needs of the library users.

References

Aufmuth, Joe (2006) *Academic Library Models for GIS and remote sensing Activities on campus*. Library Trends. 55(2)340-348.

Ardales, Venacio B. (1992) *Basic Concepts and Methods in Research*. Quezon City: Great bookstrading, Inc.

Asid, Benhur A. (2010). *The Status of Southern City Colleges' Library's Services: Basis for Development Plan*. Zamboanga City.

Buenrostro, Juan C. Jr. (2004) *More than Books Perspectives on the Management of Information Resources and Services in Libraries*. Philippines: great Books Trading, inc.

Cantwell, Jacqueline. (2012) *Librarians need to READ: a call for a collaborative effort to develop a reference interview training manual*.

<http://go.galegroup.com/ps/i.do?id=GALE%7CA260241611&v=2.1&u=phuz&it=r&p=SPJ.SPP00&sw=w>.

Claravall, Nora J. (2005) *Managing Libraries and Information Centers in the Philippine setting*. Benguet State University.

Escalona, Juliet V. *The libQual+ Approach to Measure the Library User's Perception and Expectation of Digital Library Services of the University of Santo Tomas library*. **Ad VERITATEM: University of Santo Tomas Journal**, 654-655.

Ingersoll, Patricia (2004) *Managing Information Technology*. London: Libraries Unlimited Greenwood Pub.

Levine, Amy.(2009)*The virtual librarian:reference enters the 21st century*.<http://gogalegroupcom/ps/i.do?id=GALE%7CA210337324&v=2.1&u=p&it=r8p=SPJ.SP00&sw=w>

Kaushik, Prashant (2006) *Library and Information Technology*. New Delhi: anmol Publications.

Ramos, Mariam S. (2011) *Reference 2.0 in Action: An Evaluation of the Digital Reference Services in Selected Philippine Academic Libraries*. <http://conference.ifla.org/ifla77>.

Salinas, Fabiola Elena R. (2010) *Reference Services at the Chamber of Deputies library: the present*. Library trends.

Tarranza, Rosmindor C. (2006). *The Utilization of the Library and Information Center by the Clients of Universidad de Zamboanga: Basic for the Three: Year Integrated Library Utilization Development Plan*. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation Liceo de Cagayan University. Cagayan de Oro City:

e-resources:

<https://referencephsusm.wordpress.com/2012/08/28/why-do-we-need-reference-services/>

<http://alianet.alia.org.au/publishing/ali/53.3/full.text/haynes.html>, (December 10, 2009). 2:35 p.m.

https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1300/J120v31n66_17?journalCode=wref20

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228485797_Reference_Services_in_a_University_Library_Awareness_and_Perception_of_Undergraduate_Students

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3193369/>

